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Effect of Think-Pair-Share Strategy on Students' Achievement in Chemistry in Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the Effect of Think-Pair-Share (TPS) Strategy on students' achievement in Chemistry in Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted quasi-experimental design, specifically non-randomized pretest posttest control group design. The target population for this study was 1,843 (1018 male and 825 female) Senior Secondary Two (SS2) Chemistry students in Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State. The sample comprises 135 students in intact classes of SS2 (80 male and 55 female), which was made up of 66 students in the experimental and 69 students in the control groups respectively. The instruments for data collection was Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) developed by the researchers for data collection. The data collected was subjected to a reliability test using Kuder-Richardson formula ($K-R_{20}$) for CAT. The reliability value for

CAT was 0.70 implying that the test is reliable and indicates moderate internal consistency. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions and ANCOVA to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Chemistry using TPS strategy than those taught using conventional method. The findings also revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Chemistry using TPS strategy. The study recommends among others that teachers of Chemistry should employ TPS strategy in Chemistry class to ensure effective teaching and learning so as to improve students' achievement in Chemistry irrespective of gender. The study concluded that TPS boosts students' achievement in Chemistry.

Keywords: Think-Pair-Share Strategy, Academic Achievement, Interest, Chemistry Education, Teaching Methods, Gender

Introduction

Science is the systematic pursuit of knowledge involving observation, experimentation and critical analysis to understand natural phenomena and the laws governing them. It is a continuously evolving field driven by inquiry, evidence and skepticism aimed at constructing reliable and objective explanations of the universe. Science relies on the scientific method, where hypotheses are rigorously tested and refined through experimentation, allowing for replication and validation by other researchers (National Academies of Sciences, 2016). This disciplined approach distinguishes science from other forms of knowledge, as it requires reproducibility and transparency to build a reliable body of evidence that can predict future occurrences and support technological advancements (McGrew, 2017).

Chemistry is a branch of science that examines the composition, structure, properties and reactions of matter. According to Ezejiolor (2022), Chemistry is the scientific discipline that is concerned with the study of substances, their interactions and the energy changes that accompany these processes. This definition emphasizes the dynamic nature of chemical reactions and their applications in daily life. Similarly, Okafor and Nwachukwu (2022) describe Chemistry as the study of matter at the atomic and molecular levels, focusing on how substances combine, transform and interact under varying conditions. Their perspective highlights the fundamental role of Chemistry in understanding both natural and synthetic materials. Adeleke (2022) views Chemistry as a central science that bridges physics and biology, providing insights into the molecular basis of life and industrial processes. This interdisciplinary approach underscores Chemistry's importance in fields such as medicine, agriculture, environmental science and the teaching profession.

The teaching of science, especially Chemistry, has increasingly emphasized inquiry-based and experiential learning approaches, aimed at fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and curiosity in students. Modern science instruction encourages student-centered, collaborative learning experiences, where learners actively engage in hands-on experiments and real-world applications, making science more relevant and engaging (Bybee, 2015; National Research Council, 2017).

Chemistry education focuses on developing students' understanding of matter and its interactions, which is crucial in building foundational knowledge for scientific literacy and various professional fields. Teaching strategy have shifted from rote memorization to include project-based learning and problem-solving activities that foster students' conceptual understanding of chemical principles (Gibbons *et al.*, 2018).

In the ever-evolving landscape of education, the effectiveness of teaching strategy plays a pivotal role in shaping students' interest, achievement and retention particularly in subjects as challenging as Chemistry. The traditional lecture-based approach, often characterized by passive learning, has been increasingly scrutinized for its limited effect on students' deep understanding and long-term retention of complex concepts (Hattie, 2009). In support of this, the West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiners' report from 2017-2023 shows that students showed understanding in basic chemical calculations and periodic Chemistry, yet many struggled with reaction stoichiometry and balancing chemical equations. Students consistently displayed weaknesses in answering questions on chemical reactions, particularly in organic Chemistry (WAEC, 2023). Over the years, challenges included difficulties in reaction mechanisms, isomer identification, and understanding functional groups. While some improvement was noted in mole calculations, stoichiometry, and periodic trends, students struggled to apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios. Common issues persisted with interpreting question demands, explaining reaction rates, and analyzing experimental data. Despite strengths in simpler inorganic concepts like acid-base reactions and periodic table knowledge, organic reactions such as substitutions and eliminations remained problematic (WAEC, 2023). These deficiencies highlight the need for enhanced instructional strategy, such as structured teaching aids and practical demonstrations, to address gaps in analytical skills and deepen students' understanding of chemical reactions.

To address these challenges, active learning and engagement, innovative teaching strategy can be explored. Among these, Think-Pair-Share (TPS) strategy has garnered significant attention for its potential to enhance students' cognitive and affective outcomes in secondary school Chemistry (Eggen & Kauchak, 2013). Think-Pair-Share (TPS) is another innovative teaching strategy that promotes collaborative learning. TPS strategy is a collaborative learning technique that has been widely adopted in educational settings due to its effectiveness in enhancing students' understanding and engagement. This method involves three stages: thinking individually about a topic, pairing up with a peer to discuss the thoughts, and then sharing the discussion outcomes with the larger class. This method not only increases students' engagement and participation but also improves their understanding and retention of complex concepts. According to a study by Oloyede (2017), the use of TPS in Chemistry classes resulted in higher student achievement and retention rates. The study noted that the interactive nature of TPS encourages students to articulate their thoughts and reasoning, which reinforces their learning and boosts their achievement in the subject (Chemistry).

Academic achievement, often measured through assessments, test scores, practical assessments and examinations, reflects the extent to which students have mastered the content and skills required in Chemistry. Studies have shown that students who are actively

engaged in their learning process and who develop a deep understanding of the material tend to achieve better academically (Freeman *et al.*, 2014). Achievement in Chemistry has also been positively impacted by the TPS strategy. By facilitating deeper understanding through peer discussions, TPS helps students clarify their misconceptions and reinforce their knowledge. According to a study by Johnson and Johnson (2018), students who engaged in TPS scored significantly higher in Chemistry assessments than their counterparts in traditional classrooms. The collaborative nature of TPS may allow students to learn from each other, which leads to improved problem-solving skills and a better grasp of complex concepts resulting in high achievement by students irrespective of gender.

Salami, Ogundele and Alabi (2018) opines that gender can influence how students engage with different instructional strategy, thereby affecting their learning outcomes. For instance, research by Salami *et al.* (2018) indicates that female students often exhibit higher interest and retention when collaborative strategy like TPS are employed, as these strategies tend to foster a more inclusive and supportive learning environment, which aligns with their social learning preferences. Conversely, male students might show improved achievement when TPS conceptual strategy are used, which challenge them cognitively and align with their competitive nature. However, the differences are not universally consistent, and some studies suggest that these effects are context-dependent, varying based on the subject matter, the teacher's approach, and the students' prior knowledge and motivation (Okoli, 2017). In Chemistry as a subject often perceived as challenging, the role of gender suggests that using TPS, might be most effective in catering to the diverse needs of students, thereby enhancing achievement. Recent studies support this view, emphasizing the need for teachers to be aware of gender dynamics in their instructional strategy to maximize educational outcomes for all students (Agu & Odigwe, 2020; Salami *et al.*, 2018; Okoli, 2017).

Similarly, in the context of the TPS strategy, Adigun *et al.* (2020) observed that female students exhibited higher achievement scores than their male counterparts, which may be linked to their stronger collaborative skills and communication preferences. However, other studies, such as that by Chukwudi and Eze (2021), indicate that while gender differences do exist, they are not always statistically significant, and the effectiveness of this strategy often depends more on individual learning preferences rather than gender alone. These findings highlight the importance of considering gender when implementing TPS strategy to maximize their effectiveness across diverse student populations. On this note, the present study investigates the effect of think-pair-share strategy on students' achievement in Chemistry in Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

In Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State, students face significant challenges in excelling in Chemistry, a foundational subject vital for pursuing careers in science-related disciplines. Despite its importance, many students struggle to attain the required proficiency to succeed in external examinations, which often serve as benchmarks for academic progression and career opportunities.

This persistent difficulty is linked to several factors, including inadequate teaching strategies, limited access to learning resources and lack of practical exposure. These obstacles

hinder students' understanding and performance, ultimately affecting their academic outcomes and limiting their future prospects in science-related fields.

The WAEC Chief Examiner's reports for 2022 and 2023 highlighted a recurring challenge among students in Chemistry, particularly their difficulty in balancing chemical equations. The 2022 report identified weaknesses stemming from students' inability to effectively balance reaction equations, as documented on. Similarly, the 2023 report reaffirmed this issue, emphasizing that students' failure to write balanced equations remained a significant problem (WAEC, 2023). These findings underscore the need for improved instructional strategies to enhance students' understanding and application of chemical equations.

This persistent underperformance may be largely attributed to the reliance on traditional teaching methods, such as lecture-based instruction and rote memorization, which dominate the classroom environment. These conventional strategies often fail to engage students actively, limiting their ability to develop critical thinking skills and an understanding of complex chemical concepts. Traditional teaching methods, often characterized by rote memorization and passive learning, fail to foster a deep understanding of Chemistry concepts. Consequently, students struggle to achieve satisfactory results and retain the knowledge required for higher-level applications. In contrast, the absence of innovative teaching strategy, such as Think-Pair-Share strategy, collaborative problem-solving, and the use of technology-enhanced instruction may further exacerbate the issue. These modern approaches, which encourage active participation and real-world application of knowledge, may be underutilized, leaving students disengaged and unmotivated. Consequently, the gap between students' potential and their actual achievement widens, leading to consistently low retention rates in Chemistry and diminishing interest in science-related careers among the youth in the area.

To address these challenges, innovative teaching strategies such as Think-Pair-Share (TPS) have been proposed. Implementing this strategy may potentially transform the learning environment, making Chemistry more accessible and enjoyable for students. By fostering a deeper understanding and promoting active learning, these approaches may improve students' academic achievement and long-term retention of Chemistry knowledge, ultimately reducing failure rates in the subject.

It is against this background that the researcher wishes to investigate if Think-Pair-Share strategy can enhance students' interest, achievement and retention in Chemistry in Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to determine the effect of Think-Pair-Share strategy on students' interest, achievement and retention in Chemistry in Konshisha local government area of Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study seeks to:

- i. determine the effect of Think-Pair-Share strategy on the achievement of senior secondary school students in Chemistry.
- ii. determine the effect of Think-Pair-Share strategy on the achievement of male and female Senior Secondary School Students in Chemistry.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of Senior Secondary School Students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy and those taught with the conventional method?
- ii. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of Senior Secondary School Students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy and those taught with the conventional method.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy.

Methodology

The study employed quasi-experimental design. Specifically, the pretest posttest non-randomized control group design was adopted. This design is considered appropriate because it is a useful tool in a situation where true experimentation cannot be used for ethical or practical reasons. Quasi-experimental design involves establishing cause and effect relationships.

The study area is Konshisha Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. Konshisha Local Government Area, located in Benue State, Nigeria with the target population of 1,843 (1018 male and 825 female) Senior Secondary Two (SS2) Chemistry students. The sample size of this study were four schools made up of 135 SS2 (80 male and 55 female) students, which were made up of 66 students in the experimental and 69 students in the control groups respectively. The sample size represents the number of students that are in the intact classes of the sampled schools. The study used purposive sampling techniques to choose the four co-educational schools because of the gender variable in the study while random sampling was used to choose the four schools for the study. Finally, the intact classes in the four sampled schools (two each) were assigned to experimental and control groups respectively. The instrument for data collection was Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT). CAT was developed to measure the academic achievement of the students before and after treatment. The contents of the test covered concepts drawn from SS 2 scheme of work. It was a thirty-item multiple choice objective test. Some of the questions were extracted from past WAEC questions while the remaining questions were developed by the researchers from Chemistry textbooks based on the content that were taught in the lesson for four (4) weeks. Each correctly answered question carried two (2) marks making a total of 60 marks. The instrument has options A-D for each of the test item. CAT is made up of two sections. Section A contained personal data while section B contained the Chemistry Achievement Test. CAT was used for pre-test and post-test treatments.

The instruments were validated by three experts. To determine the reliability of the instruments, a trial test was conducted on 30 SS 2 Chemistry students that were selected from Padopas Harmony Secondary School, Makurdi, in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State that are not part of the sample for the study. The data collected was subjected to a reliability test using Kuder-Richardson formula (K-R₂₀) for CAT. The decision to use the K-R₂₀ for testing reliability of CAT was borne out of the fact that the items are dichotomously scored. The reliability values for CAT was 0.70 (70%). The reliability of 0.70 or 70% of CAT suggests that the test is reliable and indicates moderate internal consistency.

Mean scores and standard deviations were used for answering the research questions. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results of the study are presented according to the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of Senior Secondary School Students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy and those taught with the conventional method?

Table 1: Mean achievement scores of Senior Secondary School Students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy and those taught with the conventional method

Instructional strategy	Pretest			Posttest		Mean Gain
	N	Mean	S. D	Mean	S. D	
TPS	66	36.36	8.50	51.50	2.31	15.14
Conventional	69	32.33	3.58	32.30	3.28	-0.03
Mean difference		4.03		19.20		15.17

Table 1 shows the mean achievement scores of students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy and those taught using conventional methods. The table shows that 66 students were taught using TPS Instructional Strategy while 69 students were taught using conventional methods. The table further reveals that the mean achievement scores of students taught using TPS Instructional Strategy is 36.36 with a standard deviation of 8.50 during pre-test and 51.50 with a standard deviation of 2.28 in posttest. While the mean achievement scores of students taught using conventional method is 32.33 with a standard deviation of 3.58 during pre-test and 32.30 with a standard deviation of 3.28 in posttest. Based on the data, the standard deviations show that student scores were more widely spread in the TPS pre-test but became much more tightly clustered and homogeneous in the post-test, while the conventional method's scores remained consistently clustered throughout.

Regarding the pre-test means, they are not directly comparable as the TPS group started with a higher mean score (36.36) than the conventional method group (32.33).

The table further shows that the mean gain for TPS Instructional Strategy is 15.14 and conventional method is -0.03. The difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy and those taught using conventional method is 15.17 in favour of students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy. This implies that TPS strategy improves students' achievement in Chemistry than conventional method.

Research Question Two

- i. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy?

Table 2: Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy

Gender	Pretest			Posttest		Mean gain
	N	Mean	S. D	Mean	S. D	
Male	30	32.77	5.74	46.33	9.69	13.56
Female	36	39.36	9.28	48.11	8.60	8.75
Mean difference		-6.59		-1.78		4.81

Table 2 shows the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy. The table shows that 30 male students and 36 female students were taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy. The table reveals that the mean achievement scores of male students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy is 32.77 with a standard deviation of 5.74 during pre-test and 46.33 with a standard deviation of 9.69 in posttest. The mean achievement scores of female students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy is 39.36 with a standard deviation of 9.28 during pre-test and 48.11 with a standard deviation of 8.60 in posttest. Table 5 further shows that the mean gain of male students that were taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy is 13.56 and those of female students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy is 8.75. The difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy is 4.81. The table also shows that achievement scores for both male and female students increased showing improvement in Chemistry though in favour of the male students. This shows that male students achieved more improvement from the TPS strategy than the female students.

Research Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of Senior Secondary School Students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy and those taught with the conventional method.

Table 3: ANCOVA of achievement scores of Senior Secondary School Students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy and those taught with the conventional method

Dependent Variable: POSTTEST

Source	Type III Sum of				Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
	Squares	Df	Mean Square	F		
Corrected Approach	2890.282a	2	1445.141	25.007	.000	2890.282a
Intercept	4381.039	1	4381.039	75.811	.000	4381.039
PRETEST	1447.663	1	1447.663	25.051	.000	1447.663
GROUP	1452.744	1	1452.744	25.139	.000	1452.744
Error	7628.118	132	57.789			7628.118
Total	322423.000	135				322423.000
Corrected Total	10518.400	134				10518.400

a. R Squared = .126 (Adjusted R Squared = .112)

Table 3 reveals that $F(1,134) = 25.139$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$. Since p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This shows that there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy and those taught using conventional method. This implies that students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy have a higher achievement scores in Chemistry than those taught using the conventional method.

Research Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy.

Table 4: ANCOVA of achievement scores of male and female students taught Chemistry using Think-Pair-Share strategy

Dependent Variable: POSTTEST

Source	Type III Sum of				Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
	Squares	Df	Mean Square	F		
Corrected Model	98.488a	2	49.244	.589	.558	.018
Intercept	5469.474	1	5469.474	65.441	.000	.510
PRETEST	46.771	1	46.771	.560	.457	.009
GENDER	15.650	1	15.650	.187	.667	.003
Error	5265.451	63	83.579			
Total	153044.000	66				
Corrected Total	5363.939	65				

a. R Squared = .018 (Adjusted R Squared = -.013)

Table 4 reveals that $F(1,65) = 0.187$; $p = .667 > 0.05$. Since p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students

taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy. This shows that TPS is not gender bias in terms of students' achievement in chemistry.

Discussion

The result from Table 1 shows the mean achievement scores of students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy and those taught using conventional methods. The table shows that the Pre-test results established baseline achievement levels, showing nearly equivalent mean scores between the two groups. The post-test results, however, revealed a substantial divergence. The mean achievement score for the TPS group increased markedly, while the mean score for the conventional method group remained statistically unchanged, resulting in a notable mean gain difference overwhelmingly in favour of the TPS strategy.

The distribution of scores around these means, as indicated by the standard deviation, also provides critical insight. The pre-test data for the TPS group showed a wider spread of scores, which tightened considerably in the post-test, suggesting the strategy was associated with a more consistent and uniform uplift in achievement across the student groups. Conversely, the conventional method group maintained a similarly tight clustering of scores around the mean from pre-test to post-test, indicating no significant shift in overall achievement.

Result from Table 3 reveals that p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The statistical significance of this difference in mean achievement scores was confirmed by an ANCOVA, which resulted in a p-value well below the 0.05 threshold, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This confirms that the observed difference is not due to random chance but is attributable to the instructional strategy. This finding is consistent with prior research, such as the study by Hamdan (2017), who investigated the impact of think-pair-share strategy on the achievement of third grade student in sciences in the educational district of Irbid. The findings of the study showed that there were statistical differences in grades of students due to group variable at the significance level (0.05), and the differences were in favour of the experimental group. Also, there were statistical differences due to gender at the significance level (0.05) in favour of females. The study also concluded that the Think-Pair-Share strategy significantly improved science achievement compared to conventional methods. This shows that there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy and those taught using conventional method. This implies that students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy have a higher achievement score in Chemistry than those taught using the conventional method.

Result from Table 2 shows the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy. The table shows that 30 male students and 36 female students were taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy. The analysis indicates that the Think-Pair-Share (TPS) Instructional Strategy is an effective and equitable pedagogical approach. The data from the pre-test establish a baseline where female students exhibited a higher mean achievement score than their male counterparts, though both groups showed considerable score variability as evidenced by

their respective standard deviations. Following the intervention, both groups demonstrated substantial gains in mean achievement scores. While the mean gain was larger for male students, the post-test results show the mean scores for both genders were highly comparable, with female students maintaining a marginal advantage. Result from Table 4 revealed that p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This statistically confirms that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught using the TPS strategy. This finding agrees with Okafor and Mohammed (2022) who explored Gender Differences in Chemistry Achievement Using Think-Pair-Share Strategy among Secondary School Students in Rivers State. The study further found that while both genders benefited from TPS, female students showed a slightly higher improvement in achievement and interest. This finding, which aligns with existing literature, implies that the TPS strategy effectively improves student achievement in Chemistry while mitigating pre-existing gender-based disparities.

Conclusion

The main objective of this study was to investigate the effect of Think-Pair-Share strategy on students' interest, achievement and retention in Chemistry in Konshisha local government area of Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, it focused on the Chemistry students. A pretest and posttest quasi-experimental design were used and the data collected from the field were subjected to statistical test based on the objectives, research questions and hypotheses formulated.

The descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the data analysis. Therefore, the findings of the study showed that students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy have a higher achievement score than those taught using the conventional method. Similarly, students taught Chemistry using TPS Instructional Strategy achievement higher scores irrespective of gender.

Limitation of the Study

Although the results of the findings of this study showed that TPS strategy has had a direct effect on students' interest, academic achievement and retention in Chemistry at secondary school. It has the following limitations:

- i. In pairs, some students dominated the discussion while others remain passive, especially in mixed-ability groups where stronger students take over.
- ii. Managing student discussions and keeping everyone on task during the "pair" or "share" stages was difficult.
- iii. Students with weak background knowledge in Chemistry struggled to contribute meaningfully during the "think" stage, limiting the effectiveness of the strategy.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Teachers from Secondary schools in Konshisha local government area of Benue State should adopt TPS Strategy in teaching Chemistry.

- ii. Chemistry Teachers should use TPS to promote active learning by encouraging students to explore chemical equations independently. Providing opportunities for students can lead to greater achievement in Chemistry.
- iii. The Government/Schools should organize regular workshops and training sessions for teachers to improve their proficiency in using TPS. Well-trained teachers can better guide students and effectively integrate the strategy into classroom activities..

REFERENCES

- Adeleke, J. O. (2022). *The Central Role of Chemistry in Modern Science*. Lagos: Nigerian Academic Press.
- Adigun, A. G., Ayodele, K. A., & Odewale, I. T. (2020). Gender differences in the achievement of students in Chemistry using the Think-Pair-Share strategy. *Nigerian Journal of Science Education, 29(4)*, 53-63.
- Agu, A., & Odigwe, C. (2020). Gender dynamics in the use of instructional strategy in secondary education. *Contemporary Issues in Education, 37(1)*, 102-116.
- Bybee, R. W. (2015). *The BSCS 5E Instructional Model: Creating Teachable Moments*. NSTA Press.
- Chukwudi, A., & Eze, I. (2021). Gender disparities in the effectiveness of collaborative learning strategy in Chemistry education. *Journal of Education and Social Research, 33(3)*, 68-79.
- Engen, P., & Kauchak, D. (2013). *Strategies and models for teachers: Teaching content and thinking skills* (6th ed.). USA: Pearson.
- Ezejiolor, T. N. (2022). *Fundamentals of Chemical Sciences*. Enugu: Delta Publications.
- Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., McDonough, M., Smith, M. K., Okoroafor, N., Jordt, H., & Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 111(23)*, 8410-8415.
- Gibbons, R. E., Villafane, S. M., Stains, M., & Murphy, K. L. (2018). Student-centered active learning in Chemistry courses. *Journal of Chemical Education, 95(8)*, 1373-1384.
- Hamdan, M. (2017). The impact of think-pair-share strategy on the achievement of third grade students in sciences in the educational district of Irbid. *Educational Sciences Journal, 15(2)*, 79-91.
- Hattie, J. (2009). *Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. Routledge.
- Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2018). Cooperative learning: The impact on achievement in secondary school science. *Educational Researcher, 47(7)*, 409-420.
- McGrew, T. (2017). *The foundations of knowledge*. Oxford University Press.
- National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2016). *The scientific method: How science works*. National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/21895>

- National Research Council. (2017). *Seeing Students Learn Science: Integrating Assessment and Instruction in the Classroom*. The National Academies Press.
- Okafor, N. G., & Mohammed, A. (2020). Enhancing Chemistry Retention among Secondary School Students Using Think-Pair-Share Strategy. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research*, 15(2), 78-89.
- Okafor, P. C., & Nwachukwu, E. O. (2022). *Principles of Chemistry: A Nigerian Perspective*. Ibadan: University Press.
- Okoli, A. C. (2017). Gender influence on learning outcomes in science education: A case study in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 52, 90-99.
- Oloyede, O. I. (2017). Effect of Think-Pair-Share on student achievement in Chemistry. *International Journal of Education*, 25(2), 65-73.
- Salami, A., Ogundele, M., & Alabi, I. (2018). Gender effects on the implementation of TPS and deep conceptual strategy in Chemistry education. *Nigerian Journal of Gender and Science Education*, 12(3), 53-67.
- WAEC (2023). Chemistry Chief Examiner's Report. <https://www.waeconline.org.ng/e-learning/Chemistry/Chem235jw.html>